

ANDRAGOGY IN ELT: AN IMPACTFUL METHODOLOGY

Dr. Kalyana Chakravarthi Thirunagari

International English Trainer Ministry of Preschool and School Education, Uzbekistan

E-mail: chekri2005@gmail.com | Mobile: +998-901186325

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Abstract. The focus of this article is on an effective English Language Teaching method called ‘Andragogy’ which is popular among ELT experts across the world. The Author emphasizes the use of this methodology in classroom practices while dealing with young adults. It becomes more essential to use this method while dealing with EFL learners that too in a country like Uzbekistan where most of the learners are first generation English learners who are trying to be proficient in English which is their second (L2) or third language (L3).

Keywords: Andragogy, methodology, ELT, EFL, L2, L3, first generation learners, public education

In this article, the author who trained 295 English Teachers so far in Uzbekistan, shares his hands-on teaching experience, Master Classes and Workshops for Teachers and 210 university Students in Khorezm region, Uzbekistan and analyses some existing Textbook exercises and activities prescribed for the English learners in the Public Education schools of Uzbekistan.

Introduction

Andragogy means the study of science and practice of adult learning. This is entirely different from Pedagogy, which is used while dealing with children’s learning. This methodology is widely used by ELT experts in India, Europe, UK, USA and many of the countries where English is taught in an ESL situation or where English is the first language (L1) or mother tongue.

Malcolm Knowles (1913-1977) was an influential American educator who popularised the term ‘andragogy’, the art and science of how adults learn. It describes the key characteristics of adult learners (as distinct from children ‘pedagogy’). It has become a highly influential adult learning theory and continues to shape learning design today. Andragogy focuses on the process of learning, rather than the product. It supports discovery-based learning, encouraging learners to construct their own understanding through problem-solving and collaboration with peers.

Andragogy: Adult Learning Theory

Source: <https://instructionaldesign.com.au/andragogy-adult-learning-theory>

Explanation

The study conducted by the author revealed that many English Teachers are still depending on Grammar Translation Method (GTM). It is observed that they are using teacher-centered methods also while teaching. It is suggested that Teachers can try to use learner-centered methods such as Andragogy which emphasizes involvement, motivation, exploration and purpose of learning by Adults.

A close look at the existing text books prescribed for the English language learners in Secondary level of public schools reveals many things about the purpose, objectives, tasks, activities and methodology being implemented in the classrooms by local and foreign teachers of English. The Ministry of Preschool and School Education has prescribed useful books for classroom delivery such as Student Book (SB), Workbook (WB) and there is a Teachers book (TB) also. All the above are designed and developed by the British and adapted by the Uzbek experts and published in collaboration with the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), Cambridge University Press (CPU) and the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Purpose

It is mentioned in the initial pages of the English Text books prescribed for the Secondary Schools in Uzbekistan as: “We hope that learning English with this book will help you achieve your ‘future goals’.”

Objectives

It is clearly mentioned that it is to provide ‘an enjoyable and fun experience’ for learners

Tasks and Activities

The prescribed text books are filled with all the four language skills such as L, S, R and W. The focus of this paper is on various Projects suggested at the end of each Unit in the Student Books (SBs).

Methodology

Though English teachers in every school in Uzbekistan follow suggested methods of teaching, they usually tend to translate many things in to local Uzbek language while teaching in the classes for the convenience of students. Temporarily, this might help but in the long run the target language, English, may not be achieved. Students must be given ample chances to think, learn, practice and use English first. If it is difficult to understand, only then local language translation can be tried out.

The following Tasks and Activities are prescribed in the text books. Very few Teachers try to implement these things in their classes involving the students. The author conducted several Master Classes in the Khorezm region, Uzbekistan and made the English Teachers study and implement these Projects in their respective classes.

The list below shows the Project titles, Objectives and Outcomes of the activities conducted in the classes:

Name of Project	Objectives
1) A video presentation	- to improve speaking, reading by using new technology
2) Research a training school & a market	- to improve writing, speaking - to enhance S.W.V
3) A poster about internet safety	- to improve vocabulary and speaking skills
4) An environmental campaign	- to enhance cooperative learning and speaking as well as using technology
5) A school web page	- improve vocabulary, speaking and critical thinking skills
6) Ways to keep fit	- to enhance speaking vocabulary, reading skills
7) Description a national park	- to improve pupils' creativity, speaking and writing skills
8) Sharing resources	- to enhance working individually, critical thinking, problem-solving ability
9) A book club and author post file	- to improve reading comprehension and speaking skills
10) A campaign about fake news	- to exchange ideas, get extra information
11) Resolving a conflict	- to improve problem-solving ability, speaking and writing skills
12) A presentation about a film	- to improve speaking
13) A food guide	- to enhance writing
14) The history of a sport	- to improve writing, vocabulary & speaking

Fig 1: Enlisted Projects and Objectives in SBs

The figure below shows the elicitation of the answers by the author during the interaction with the Teachers while conducting Master Classes for the English Teachers, Khorezm region, Uzbekistan.

The questions asked to the Teachers are as follows:

1. What are the Skills that you usually focus on in your English classes?
2. What are the Methods that you generally use in your classes?
3. What Activities are used in your classes?
4. What type of Tasks are conducted in your classes?
5. Which are the important methods for you?
6. Which Tasks and Activities are less important in English books?

PROJECT	MASTER CLASS-7	29/2/2024
Creative Writing		Thursday
1.	Listening, S, R, W, Grammar	
2.	Audio-Lingual, GTM, Suggestopedia, TPR, DM Reading out, HO, Discussion	
3.	Individual Pairwork, Role Plays, Dictation, Memory games, tables stories	
4.	Gap-filling, MCQ, matching, Reading exercise, True/False	
5.	GTP, CLT	
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Speaking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Writing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Listening

Fig 2: The Methods, Tasks and Activities done by English Teachers in Uzbekistan.

The questions asked to the Students are as follows:

1. Do you know that there are Projects mentioned at the end of every Unit in your SB?
2. What Projects have you completed in your SB?
3. Write some benefits of doing Projects.
4. Which skills have you acquired by doing these Projects?
5. How many of your classmates attempted these Projects?
6. Which other Projects/ Topics do you need in future?

The above survey questionnaire was given to the 58 students of Grade 11 in the class and they were asked to write answers. The result is quite amazing. Some have done few Projects and many students haven't done these Projects. Few intelligent and serious students have touched upon these Projects. Out of 54 Students of Grade 11, only 25 students have participated in these Projects directly or indirectly. They could have done these with the help of English teachers of respective schools.

Andragogy can work in these cases where the learners' interest levels are low or not up to the mark at the schools in Uzbekistan. Doing Projects is an essential learning activity if implemented by the Teachers and participated by the Students here.

Fig 3: Questionnaire on Tasks and Activities done by the Students

The answers are as follows:

1. We have 15 Projects in our SB. Shopping is the most comfortable Project.

There are some learnings like problem-solving, collaboration, time management, risk mitigation, about shopping while doing these Projects. We formed groups for Project. There was socializing. Culture, Animals, Cooking, Getting Around, Summer camps, presentation, a poster about a celebrity, report, shopping habits,

2. We learned new information. We know the prices of things and interacted in group.

3. We learnt Report Writing, Creativity, Listening and Communication. We learned about shopping, fashion and income in these Projects. We have taken some videos in this Project. We learnt Time management.

4. 35 students attempted these Projects.

5. We need topics on Education, Travel, Social media, Conservation of nature and Team work in future Projects.

Observation and Analysis

Most of the methods and Activities are done usually in the above classes, but certain important activities like Projects are left or given less importance by the English Teachers here.

The figure above doesn't show 'Projects' in the list which indicates that they are not doing it properly.

Doing Projects in English classes gives ample chances to learners, they try to put their hands, head and heart into these activities which makes them learn by themselves, interact with others, transfer knowledge from one another and discover new skills and knowledge. All the above are important ingredients of Andragogy. This essential thing is missing in the methodology followed by the Teachers in ELT here. The author emphasizes this aspect in his Workshops and Master Classes frequently.

The outcomes of the above activities is very important for measuring the learning of target language which gives a fair idea of what else can be done in future for the students. This can be done at the end of each Project.

Suggestions

The author as an ELT expert, Trainer and Researcher, based on his experiences in Uzbekistan, suggests the following:

- The English Teachers must try to use as much English as possible in their classes
- Translation of English to Uzbek should be minimized and used in very difficult situations where understanding English becomes impossible for the learners
- Follow and implement Andragogy while dealing with secondary level learners
- There should be regular monitoring on various tasks and activities implementation in English classes
- The local educational authorities of various districts and provinces, Teacher Training Institutes and the Ministry of Preschool and School Education can conduct regular interactions between schools of different districts and provinces to ensure best practices in Teaching-Learning process periodically involving ELT experts and Foreign Teachers employed in various regions of Uzbekistan
- A National Project on implementation, monitoring and adaptation of existing Materials, Methods and Testing can be initiated by the Ministry of Public Education involving local and Foreign English Teachers in Uzbekistan.

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